

Cloud platforms Lead to Open and Universal access for people with Disabilities and for All

D401.3. UCD and style-guide usage in the project

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Statement of originality

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List of abbreviations

Table 2. List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
HiFi	High Fidelity
LoFi	Low Fidelity
MeFi	Medium Fidelity
PCP	Personal Control Panel
PMT	Preference Management Tool
UCD	User-Centred Design
UI	User Interface
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

SP4 is focused on testing the ideas, concepts, and methods identified or developed by the Cloud4all project in real world settings. To foster this, a user population and UCD Implementation Plan (D401.1) and a UCD style guide (D401.2) were created in the first year of the project. This guide gives advice for the creation of User Interfaces, both applicable to a variety of settings and to automatic adaptations. The current document describes how these two documents have been used along the whole project duration to ensure that the UCD approach is adopted and applied in the design and development of interfaces and applications.

To that end, this document details the UCD approach applied in the design and development of interfaces and applications: from one hand through all the activities for user involvement in the design and research activities, and from the other, the interaction plan that included context of usage and requirement analysis, conceptual design and prototyping and evaluation.

The user involvement along the whole project has been successful thanks to the plan followed for recruitment and liaison with users groups, that allowed the participation of 353 end-users, 77 developers and 45 stakeholders in research activities.

Moreover, Cloud4all adopted a UCD process planned through the three iterations in order to identify potential errors and improve designs and solutions timely. Together with the UI style guide, intended to ensure that interfaces could be transformed according to individual user's needs and preferences, a set of controlling mechanisms were defined in order to assure that all design & development and testing activities were conducted in agreement with the UCD plan and the feedback gathered was communicated to the design and development teams.

2 Introduction

2.1 Objectives of this document

This document is the outcome of activities included in *WP401: Methodologies for user involvement*. These activities aim at fulfilling the following operational objectives:

- OO.8.1: To ensure adequate representation of beneficiaries and stakeholders in user testing, by identifying and recruiting all those groups and persons that will participate in project Pilots.
- OO.8.2: To guarantee a strong level of engagement from the same test participants, as much as possible, throughout all evaluation phases of the project, and thus get comparable and evolving opinions on the maturity of various project prototypes, as they are iteratively tested and optimized.
- OO.8.3: To organize a test plan, that will guide the design, development and evaluation of the research, involving users from the very beginning and following a user centered approach a guarantee of success.
- OO.8.4: To validate the designs and developments of the UI interfaces against a style guide, optimally reflecting good usability and accessibility principles from the literature, offering a good starting point for project's further UI adaptation and autoconfiguration.
- OO.8.5: To guarantee that the project procedures are compliant with the user centered approach defined in this WP, through a set of controlling mechanisms.

This document summarized the procedures followed in the project in order to ensure that the UCD approach is adopted and applied in the design and development of interfaces and applications.

2.2 Relationship with other WPs and activities

This document is mainly related to two previous deliverables from WP401:

- *D401.1. Cloud4All user population and UCD Implementation Plan* (Sainz de Salces, Melcher, Ochoa & Cheetam, 2012). This document defines the different user groups involved in Cloud4all and the procedures for their recruitment and involvement. Moreover, it stated the UCD approach to be adopted in the project and describe a number of methodologies to be used.
- *D401.2. UI Style-guide and controlling mechanisms* (Melcher, Pawlowski & Leuteritz, 2012). This style guide provides general advice for the creation of User Interfaces,

both applicable to individually programmed solutions and to automatic adaptations. Moreover, it defined controlling mechanisms to ensure that the UCD approach is adopted in the project.

In addition to the deliverables listed below, this document is two-way related with the activities included in *WP402: Pilot frameworks and logistics* and *WP403: Iterative pilots* and their resulting deliverables. The current document describe UCD activities performed as part of the Cloud4all pilots, and the results of the evaluation activities defined and conducted in these WPs have been also used as an important input for the design and development of User Interfaces in the project.

2.3 Structure of the document

First, Section 2 describes the procedures followed for the recruitment of users and the liaison with user groups, together with the main results in terms of number of users involved in Cloud4all activities. Section 3 focuses on the UCD activities followed during the different phases of the interaction plan and describes their main results. Finally, section 4 presents the main conclusions of the document.

3 Recruitment and liaison with users groups

3.1 Introduction: Definition of user groups in Cloud4all

In order to introduce this section, it may be useful to provide a summary of the definition and characterization of all of the end-users, key actors and other stakeholders, that have been involved in Cloud4all and in some way will be able to take advantage of the output of the project.

3.1.1 User groups

Defining user groups is the first step to ensure that the individual participants will represent the range of needs and preferences of their group of reference. The representativeness is a key aspect that, if it is not addressed properly, could lead to a totally wrong product or service. Very frequently, people with disabilities are defined as having standard functional characteristics that rarely represents the ample range of existing disability conditions.

Although the approach adopted in this project doesn't focus on the traditional medically derived profiles of disability, it was necessary to do a classification of the profiles to be involved in the different phases of the project in order to try to represent as much as possible the wide range of problems, needs and preferences of the users in the different environments where Cloud4all will work. The classification considered that sometimes a specific kind of human functioning stands out, but also that there are mixed types due to multiple disabilities, or even because the socio-demographic conditions of the person can influence the relationship of the person with the environment. To that end, the following categories of disability or diversity in functioning were considered to be involved in UCD activities:

- **Visual impairments:** Two segments of users with visual impairments are considered, total blindness and low vision.
 - **Blind people** are those who see nothing at all or only have a slight perception of light (may be able to distinguish between light and dark, but not the shape of objects).
 - **People with low vision** are those who with the best possible correction could see or distinguish, though with great difficulty, some objects at close range. In the best of conditions, some of them can read print if it is of sufficient size and clarity, but generally more slowly, with considerable effort and using special aids. This group includes conditions as the loss of visual acuity, contrast sensitivity, colour perception, central field or peripheral vision.

- **Hearing disabilities:** These conditions are characterized by a total or very serious loss of hearing (mild, moderate, severe or profound loss). In Cloud4all only those with severe or profound hearing loss have been considered.
- **Deafblindness:** This is a complex disability resulting from the combination of hearing and visual impairments. Some deaf-blind people are totally deaf and blind, while others have residual hearing and / or visual, so-called "dual sensory loss," which means that the combined loss can be significant for the person despite not being profoundly deaf or completely blind.
- **Cognitive impairments:** Cognitive impairments refer to conditions characterized by limitations of functions of the brain, both global mental functions, such as consciousness, energy and drive, and specific mental functions, such as memory, language and calculation mental functions. In Cloud4all two specific profiles have been involved: people with intellectual disabilities and people with dyslexia.
 - **Intellectual disabilities:** This is a disability characterized by significant limitations in both intellectual functioning and in adaptive behavior, which normally develops before the age of 18 and covers many everyday social and practical skills.
 - **Dyslexia:** It is a learning disorder characterized by a reading difficulty despite having a normal intelligence.
- **Elderly people:** The ageing process involves a loss of sensory, cognitive and physical abilities which may hamper everyday activities including the use of ICT. There is no definitive age at which time people become elderly, however, in Cloud4all we have adopted the universally accepted consideration that 65+ would fall into this group.

3.1.2 Developers

Cloud4all has, as one of its goals, simplifying the development of ICT products and services. As a result, the developers of ICT products and services are among the "users" of Cloud4all and have been considered as part of the Cloud4all process.

For practical reasons, two different groups of developers have been considered in Cloud4all:

- **Internal developers:** They are developers of the Cloud4all consortium who are working in the development of applications within the SP3 of the project, so that they know the Cloud4all/GPII framework since they are even integrating their applications with Cloud4all.
- **External developers:** They are developers outside the Cloud4all consortium who don't have any experience with the project or the GPII.

3.1.3 Stakeholders

In Cloud4all, a dialogue took place with stakeholders on their proposals and priorities, their views and needs, including the results of this dialogue in the process of analysis and development. More concretely, different stakeholder profiles have been involved in the project:

- Social workers and carers of people with disabilities
- PwD organisation representatives
- Experts in specific disability profiles working at universities or governmental bodies
- Technology trainers and teachers
- AT product or service providers

3.2 Recruitment of the user population

Once the user groups and the sample composition are defined and assigned to specific research activities, it is possible to start the recruitment process that is not a straightforward one. In Cloud4all, practical strategies have been put in place to manage recruitment of people with disabilities and overcome communication barriers.

The first instance in the recruitment of people with disabilities in Cloud4all has been the production of project documentation. Different documents in accessible forms have been delivered in order to call for participation and manage the involvement of users in specific activities (see D402.2.1 – 3). After the project information was produced, it was used to support a first contact with the potential participants through different strategies:

- Through user organizations, as project partners (e.g. ONCE Foundation in Spain).
- Through user organizations, as mediators. In the cases that the organizations are not part of Cloud4all officially they can also play an intermediary role between the researchers and people with disabilities. For example, this is the case of Blindenschule Berlin in the German pilot that have been contacted through SDC.
- Search user databases from previous projects of Cloud4all organizations.
- Open call for participation. Announcements in specialized newspapers, magazines or forums and leaflets distributed in institutions, conferences or meetings are usually effective.

The following table summarizes the different profiles recruited for UCD activities in the three different iterations of Cloud4all:

Table 3. Summary of participants involved in UCD activities

User group	1 st iteration	2 nd iteration	3 rd iteration	TOTAL
Blind people	29	48	23	100
Low vision	30	31	42	103
Hearing impaired	-	9	1	10
Deafblindness	-	6	18	24
Intellectual disabilities	6	4	15	25
Dyslexia	6	-	15	21
Elderly people	16	22	18	56
Low literacy	6	-	-	6
Users without disabilities	-	-	8	8
TOTAL	93	120	140	353

In addition to these explicit evaluation activities, several beneficiaries (32 users and 17 experts) participated in preliminary activities for the definition of Cloud4all use cases (see Madrid, Peinado y Koutkias, 2012).

In practice, it is very difficult that the sample of participants involved in the project could represent the full range of needs and preferences of a certain user group, and just a sub-sample of them will participate in research activities. To mitigate this problem, we adopted a number of strategies in Cloud4All:

- **Use a combination of constructed and random samples:** 50% of the participants in all research activities are actively selected to ensure that all key dimensions are represented (e.g. ensuring that blind Linux users are involved even when this circumstance is rare compared to blind Windows users), and 50% are selected by circumstance (e.g. the individuals are present at pilot sites or volunteer after seeing an online call for participation).
- **Replace part of the sample after each iteration:** For example, the Cloud4all project had the goal to have 50% of participants involved from the beginning and for the 4 years duration of the project. Being the development process structured in three consecutive pilot iterations, the other 50% of the sample can be new for each pilot phase, increasing the chance of representing different needs and preferences along the project.

- **Involvement of experts and stakeholders in participatory activities:** It is advisable to involve people that do not only represent themselves but also speak for their user group. A probed strategy is to include stakeholders (tutors, relatives, educators, rehabilitators, user-organizations staff, etc.) in focus groups and co-design sessions complementing the perspectives of individual with disabilities.

3.3 Liaison with end-users, developers and stakeholders

Recruiting and retaining volunteers is an essential process that will guarantee a reliable outcome regarding users input in the concept validation, co-design and design stages as well as in all the evaluations and testing activities that need to be carried out during the project.

3.3.1 Engagement with user communities at pilot sites

3.3.1.1 Greek pilot site

In Greece representatives and stakeholders forums have been established from the 1st pilot iteration and these local taskforces were contacted and retrieved users for the Cloud4All user pool. CERTH/HIT has a very wide and diverse panel of organizations of users with disabilities that are in collaboration, which covers all the user groups needed for the pilots. CERTH/HIT has participated during the last 10 years in a number of projects related to ICT and accessibility so it is closely related to people with disabilities, the elderly and other groups at risk of social exclusion, in different matters such as labour integration, education, transport and ICT. Thanks to its long experience involving end-users, CERTH/HIT counts with an own panel of users with different profiles of disabilities, age, educational level, etc. Taking advantage of this resource, part of the users involved in Greece along the different evaluation phases of the project have been recruited by this mean.

Additionally CERTH/HIT has clear guidelines concerning recruitment to ensure equality of opportunities and access (candidates must be asked the same questions; all interviewers must have been on training for equal opportunities; use of gender friendly vocabulary on job vacancies).

3.3.1.2 German pilot site

In Germany, SDC used their institutional contacts to research institutions, lobby groups and self-help group for disabled people and elderly people. Educational institution for disabled were also contacted to recruit users for the pilot tests and focus groups.

A list of institutions used for recruitment follows (in alphabetic order):

Allgemeiner Blinden- und Sehbehindertenverein Berlin, Annastift Hannover, Arbeitskreis Barrierefreies Internet, Projekt barrierefrei informieren und kommunizieren, Behindertengemeinschaft Bonn, div. Berufsbildungswerke, Blinden- und Sehbehindertenbund Hessen, Blindenschule Berlin, Blindenschule Bremen, Blista Marburg, Büro für Leichte Sprache Bremen, Capito, Deutscher Blinden- und Sehbehindertenverband, Deutscher Gehörlosenbund, Deutscher Schwerhörigenbund, Forschungsinstitut Technologie Behindertenhilfe, Forschungsstelle zur Rehabilitation von Menschen mit kommunikativer Behinderung, Fraunhofer Institut Angewandte Informationstechnik, Gebärdenswerk Hamburg, Gehörlosenverband München, HörBIZ Berlin, igl Düsseldorf, Kommunikations- und Informationszentrum für Aphasiker, Kooperation Behinderter im Internet, Martinsclub, miteinander leben Sürth, Ohrenkuss, Paritätischer Wohlfahrtsverband, Paulinenpflege, PIKSL Labor, ProSeniore, Senior Research Group TU Berlin, Senioren-Computer-Club Berlin, Sozialwerk der Hörgeschädigten, verdi Senioren Club.

3.3.1.3 Spanish pilot site

In Spain, the users' recruitment have been planned and executed through three different ways: the ILUNION Technology and Accesibility panel of users with disabilities, the involvement of end-users organisations through ONCE Foundation and the online dissemination through Discapnet website and its social networks.

The Studies and Social Research Department at ILUNION Technology and Accessibility manages social research projects related to people with disabilities, the elderly and other groups at risk of social exclusion, in different matters such as labour integration, education, transport and ICT. Thanks to its long experience involving end-users we count with an own panel of users with different profiles of disabilities, age, educational level, etc. Taking advantage of this resource, part of the users involved in Spain along the different evaluation phases of the project have been recruited by this mean.

Additionally, the other important channel for recruiting users has been through ONCE Foundation and its wide network in the disability world in Spain. The ONCE Foundation has a Board, where the major organizations of persons with disabilities in Spain are represented, such as COCEMFE, FEAPS, CNSE, FIAPAS, FEAFES and ASPACE. Also, part of the ONCE Foundation's Board is CERMI (Spanish Committee of Representatives of Persons with Disabilities), platform that brings together the main organizations of persons with disabilities in Spain. Additionally, the ILUNION Group, belonged to ONCE and its Foundation, employs about 31,000 workers, of which over 32% (about 10,000 people) have any disability. This wide range of relationships and networks has allowed the needed contacts for the recruitment of specific profiles of users during the whole project in Spain.

Finally, we have also announced the recruiting processes in a specific accessible website called “DISCAPNET” and its profile in social networks, managed by ILUNION Technology and Accessibility. DISCAPNET is the reference website for all end users and disability organizations in Spain, with more than 7 million of visits and 61 million of viewed pages every year. It comprises two main lines of action: An information service for organizations, professionals, people with disabilities and their families, and a platform for developing actions to promote participation in the economic, social and cultural life of people with disabilities. DISCAPNET, throughout its website and its mailing lists, has relation with 4153 associations, foundations, centres and enterprises related with the disability world all-around Spain.

These three ways for contacting end-users have allowed a successful recruitment of all the foreseen users for the three evaluation phases of the project in Spain.

3.3.2 Managing ethical and legal issues

A pre-requisite for the involvement of user groups is the construction of trust by adequately managing the ethical and legal issues which normally arise in any type of research, but that are even more relevant when people with disabilities are claimed to play an active role as participants (Sainz & Bustamante, 2014).

Some ethical and legal aspects that have been considered when involving users in Cloud4all are the following:

- 1. Confidentiality, privacy and data protection.** The anonymity of participants have been guaranteed, taking into account that data regarding health records or the disability profile of participants has the higher protection status in several national legislations. Moreover, specific consents have been required to take and distribute pictures or videos from users and data anonymization procedures have been applied to results and dissemination of research outcomes.
- 2. Personal safety.** It has been considered that most of the research activities in Cloud4all don't imply any potential physical harm, considering that the premises and equipment comply with the accessibility and safety regulations. However, there always exist minor risks of pshysical or psychological discomfort or inconveniences during research activities. For example, there is a chance of invoking unrealistic hopes and expectations for personal benefits in terms of access to new and better solutions, and the subsequent risk of disappointment. This has been counteracted by very explicit and adequately communicated information about the limitations of such personal benefit and also established in the explanation on the informed consent.

- 3. Informed consent.** The national and international legal regulations regarding the participation of users or patients in research has been considered in Cloud4all. Informed consents used in research activities described the rights of the participants and their role, the volunteering nature of participation, the aim of the activities and the use of the data collected. The forms were provided in accessible format so that all participants, regardless their disability, were able to read the information and sign it by their own.
- 4. Compensation.** Participants have received a compensation for their time and effort during research and development activities. This was of different type and value (i.e. cash, gift cards, cinema tickets, etc.), fixed in advance depending on the budget available for this activity and the characteristics of the tasks to be performed by users (duration, difficulty, etc.). Additionally, compensation for transport to the facilities were provided in case of specific profiles of users with mobility difficulties.
- 5. Ethical committees and controlling mechanisms.** User involvement in research have been submitted for review and approval of the Cloud4all Ethical & Legal Advisory Committee, that provided ethical guidance and controlling mechanisms for research. However, the formal requirements of ethics are also sometimes difficult to apply in practice and sometimes users have difficulties in understanding informed consents, fully ensuring privacy and confidentiality, or implementing the pre-approved data collection methods. To cope with this issue, an additional controlling mechanism adopted in Cloud4all was to evaluate with users if the ethical procedures were adequately fulfilled during their participation. An Ethical aspects evaluation form was delivered to each user participating in research activities in order to validate the procedures and identify potential issues. Although most of the users responses were positive, there were a minor number of users declaring having doubts about the procedures (e.g. not fully understand the treatment of their personal data) or having experienced minor discomforts (e.g. hot or cold environment during user tests).

3.3.3 Dissemination of research results

Dissemination activities have been shown a key instrument to maintain the commitment of people with disabilities with the project. However, very frequently the results of research are just disseminated to stakeholders and experts (i.e. research centers, universities and standardization bodies, policy makers, industrial organizations and service providers, etc.), through conferences or scientific papers, but this information doesn't really reach the end-users. Due to this, participants could be disappointed because they don't see the results of their contribution to the research activities in which they participate. It should be

emphasized that the results of these research projects should be transferred to the end-users and their environment.

In order to inform people with disabilities about the advances and outcomes of the project, different channels can be used: web portals, social networks, emails, newspapers and magazines, special events, etc. For example, project website should be the main reference for reading information about project results, so its design and contents should be adequate for all users, caring for web accessibility.

In the context of Cloud4all, two kinds of special events have been also organized to disseminate research results:

- **User forums:** Collocated with project workshops and conferences, these events provide an opportunity for the end-users as well as other stakeholders and experts, to know about the different ideas and solutions and give their technical and practical feedback, suggestions and concerns about prototypes being developed. A total of 61 end-users participated in the three user forums organized: 11 participants in the 1st user forum in Germany, 30 participants in the 2nd user forum in Greece, and 20 participants in the 3rd user forum in Spain.

Figure 1. Participants in the user forums organized in Germany, Greece and Spain

- **Open days and Demo events:** Open days are structured events lasting one or more days in order to present the most mature and close-to-market demonstrators. Moreover, conferences and exhibitions offer ample space to present demos during which user feedback can be gathered. Several events of this kind have been organized by CLOUD4all partners along the project duration (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Three Open day events organized by Cloud4all partners

4 UCD activities and results

4.1 User-Centred Design (UCD) approach in Cloud4all

4.1.1 Cloud4all interaction plan

Cloud4all adopted a UCD process as defined in *D401.1 User implementation plan (Sainz et al., 2012)*. This process was planned through three development phases: 1) Context of usage and requirement analysis, 2) Conceptual design and prototyping, and 3) Evaluation. These three phases went through three iterations in order to identify potential errors and improve designs and solutions timely. The interaction plan is summarized in the following figure:

Figure 3. Cloud4all general interaction plan

After each iteration, the focus move again to activities in phases 2 (conceptual design and prototyping) and 3 (evaluation). However, it is worth to notice that, in practice, each iteration also included actions related with phase 1 (context of usage and requirement analysis). For example, during the first iteration, creativity sessions took place to have a better knowledge of the context of usage of Cloud4all solutions. Moreover, user testing results suggested new user requirements to be implemented in the new prototypes.

4.1.2 UI style guide and controlling mechanisms

D401.2 UI style guide and controlling mechanisms was delivered at the beginning of the project in order to ensure that developers and designers cope with usability and accessibility requirements in their applications. Particularly, the UI style guide was intended to be fulfilled by the PMT, the PCP as well as any other Cloud4all application with a user interface.

The set of guidelines defined covered the following set of elements:

- Accessibility
- Main UI principles and application tasks
- Integrating UI Options and Cloud4all menus
- Window layout for large and small display devices
- Using controls in Cloud4all
- Cloud4all default colours, fonts and element styles

These guidelines were not intended to ensure the transformability of interfaces, that is, principles and practices were not defined to prescribe a specific look and feel but to ensure that interfaces could be transformed according to individual user's needs and preferences.

Together with the guidelines, a set of controlling mechanisms were defined in order to assure that all design & development and testing activities were conducted in agreement with the UCD plan and that all the essential feedback from the testing phase was indeed collected and communicated to the design and development teams. For example, a list of usability and accessibility issues were sent from the evaluation team to the UX team after each pilot iteration in order to communicate user feedback.

Following, the activities and results for each of the design and development phases are summarized. More details can be found in (Ayotte, Vass, Mitchell, & Treviranus, 2014).

4.2 Phase 1 - Context of usage and requirement analysis

4.2.1 Understanding user needs and defining use cases

Understanding user requirements is an integral part of information systems design and is critical to the success of interactive systems. On this account, a user and stakeholder analysis has been performed within the Cloud4all project to identify different users and stakeholders to document their characteristics. For the user analysis different kind of users have been taken into account, e.g. potential end-users, but also developers and stakeholders (experts, carers and trainers or policy makers) as detailed in Section 3.1.

As a result of the *WP101: User needs and Use Cases*, the concrete key applications for applying the project algorithm were selected, assuring the range of applications to develop is demanded by the user community, thus ascertaining their perceived utility. In the next stage user needs and requirements were identified and mapped to each application area of SP3. The outcome of this activity was a set functional requirements meeting the full range of user needs (see (Madrid, Peinado, & Koutkias, 2012)). Based on the previous work the key use cases and user scenarios were defined in order to initialise the first draft concepts and designs.

Two UCD-based activities were performed in this phase, namely a desktop research and a set of interviews with users and experts:

- **Desktop research:** The methodology followed had two main parts:
 - Collaborative development of scenarios of use, in which different contexts and applications were examined, identifying the full range of scenarios that could represent the range of the space.
 - Literature review, including a thorough review of user profile related standards.
- **Interviews with users and experts:** 32 people with disabilities and 17 experts were interviewed using a questionnaire in order to gather information about 1) use of applications; 2) configurations performed; 3) problems and barriers found; and 4) preferences and requirements on technology use.

4.2.2 Usability and accessibility requirements in the UI-style guide

Following the user needs tasks performed under WP101 for the understanding of user needs and the definition of use cases, additional works related to requirement analysis were conducted in WP401 in order to define the UI style-guide.

- **Focus groups:** Two focus groups were organized to get first ideas of how user interfaces within the GPII / Cloud4all could be adapted to the user needs and what requirements users have for applications developed within the Cloud4all project.
- **Desktop research:** As a second step, a review of the project and architecture requirements was performed to complement the user requirements. Based on the requirements general as well as specific guidelines were defined as recommendations for user interface design.

4.3 Phase 2 - Conceptual design and prototyping

4.3.1 Conceptual design

In the first year of the project, designers and developers focused on creating a tool that could allow users to declare their needs and preferences and to create their own one-size-fits-one interfaces. For this, the use cases and user scenarios provided in Phase 1 were used to specify first application and user interface concepts grounded in the user requirements and the approved interface guidelines. It became clear that declaring needs and preferences first required an awareness or familiarity with the notion of adjusting settings in the digital environment - an awareness that cannot be assumed for all users. The challenge, then, was

to conceive of a preference management tool that could enable and promote the discovery, adjustment and application of user preferences.

The team started by thinking extensively about the circumstances for realistic uses of the tools. To address a broad range of unique needs, the PMT must be inherently flexible and adaptable. The team also concluded that to be truly inclusive, the tool must meet each person wherever he or she is in any particular context. The following are just a few of the many unique individual and contextual factors the team considered when thinking through user interactions with digital systems:

- Environment (noisy bus station, bright sunlight shining on a screen, etc.)
- Unique user abilities (age, digital literacy, mobility, dexterity, preferred and necessary means of computer interaction, cognitive needs, etc.)
- Operating system and application variability
- Learning approaches (preferred ways of consuming content)

This list helped the design team keep the breadth and depth of contextual complexities in mind while conceptualizing interfaces for addressing user needs.

To fully meet users “wherever they are,” the UX team concluded that the tool must meet users both in the context of their current task (simpler for quick “on-the-fly” adjustments), as well as in full-featured applications that users can access at their leisure. It became clear that the design team needed to consider multiple tools to allow diverse users to discover, adjust, and apply needs and preferences. The preference management tools must allow for a range of users: first-time users getting in the door, users exploring new preferences that might meet their needs, and technology-savvy users making advanced refinements for specific customizations. The tools must also allow users to move through levels of complexity as they become more comfortable with the idea and process of setting preferences.

The ultimate vision for these tools is that they will allow users to customize any interface they might encounter by exploring and then declaring preferences, saving them to the cloud, and applying them to devices (both private and public). This personalization meets users wherever they are and adapts the interface to their needs and preferences, getting users in the door and making their interaction with technology as painless and as enjoyable as possible.

In working on the conceptual design of the PMT, two methods emerged as the most relevant and useful: mind-maps and use cases.

4.3.1.1 Mind-maps

Mind-mapping allowed the design team to tackle the big picture early on in the design process, and revealed many possibilities and questions about a desired preference editing workflow. The space of preference discovery and declaration is quite complex. Early in the design process the team developed a number of graphical mind-maps for thinking through the complex workflow of someone using the preference management tools (see **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**).

Sketching out these mind-maps allowed the design team to begin visualizing interface flows and to identify open questions related to workflow of the tools. The development of mind-maps quickly led to the need for use cases and wireframes to consider user behavior and contexts and to demonstrate the variety of interactions at each stage of the workflow.

Over the course of the design process the team returned to these mind-maps several times to refine the workflow, consider alternate workflow options, and to tweak the corresponding wireframes.

Figure 4. Preference management mind map (https://wiki.gpii.net/w/Profile_Management)

4.3.1.2 Use Cases and Scenarios

While working on the mind-maps it became clear that the team needed a way to evaluate how realistic the workflow was and to consider user behavior in more detail. As a result, the team began to develop a number of detailed use cases and related scenarios in order to consider realistic situations and user needs that needed to be addressed by the preference editing tools. At the same time, the team began to sketch wireframes in order to zero in on a level of granularity of the interface and interactions and to consider the levels of complexity of user needs.

Use cases provide a way for the design team to consider the many situations and contexts in which users might encounter and use the preference management tools. Through the development of these use cases and scenarios the team began to understand both the breadth of requirements for the tools design as well as the specifics of how to meet individual users' needs. Due to their nature, these use cases are limited because they cannot cover the full spectrum of potential users, and in no way do they replace the need for user testing. However they provided a starting point for the design team to map out various scenarios in which the preference management tools might be used and thus provided a starting-point for interface and interaction design. The use cases allowed the design team to consider a broad range of potential users including first-time computer users, power users, and users with and without assistance.

Full use case examples could be read following wiki page:
<http://wiki.fluidproject.org/display/fluid/%28C4A%29+Use+Cases>.

4.3.2 Prototyping: From paper mock-ups to high fidelity prototypes

Design concepts have been transformed into prototypes of different degree of fidelity (from paper mock-ups to high fidelity prototypes) that have been used to discuss internally and to support evaluations with users during pilots.

As the mind-maps became more detailed, the team began to sketch wireframes of the interface designs corresponding to stages in the workflow for different preference editing tools. Several iterations of wireframes were developed as the team returned to the mind-maps and use cases repeatedly.

During the first year, two LO/ME-FI functional prototypes for the PMT were designed and tested with users:

- PMT with basic functions
- PMT with advanced functions

Figure 5. Example wireframes created for PMT adjusters

- During the second year, a HI-FI prototype of the PMT were delivered as an evolution of the prototypes produced in year 1 after incorporating feedback from user testing. Moreover, two non-functional prototypes were produced as paper mock-ups and wireframes:
- PMT with extended functions and sharing among peers functionality
- PCP advanced prototype

Figure 6. Two example screenshots from the PCP advanced prototype

During the third year, works continued in the design of preference editing tools, focusing in extending functionalities for context-related changes and improving the usability of the interfaces based on previous evaluation with users.

For more examples of wireframes and updated information see <http://wiki.fluidproject.org/display/fluid/Preference+Editing+Tools+Design>.

4.4 Phase 3 - Evaluation

4.4.1 Introduction

The results of user testing and other evaluation methods have provided much benefits for the iterative development of user interfaces along the project. Especially, the user testing during the first and the second iteration phases found a set of usability and accessibility problems that were fixed in the final iteration. When an optimal user interface needs to be selected from several alternatives, a comparative usability test is useful to find out which user interface is the best.

Within Cloud4All, there were three evaluation iterations, each of which have provided a thorough feedback of the perceived usefulness, ease of access and interaction, acceptance and satisfaction of the end-users, developers and all other types of stakeholders regarding the developments of the project. After the end of each evaluation round, an internal report (e.g. ID403.1 Results from evaluation phase I) were provided to the development teams of the project for optimization in order to continue with the 2nd round and so on.

4.4.2 Feedback loop with designers and developers

Different procedures were set up along the project to serve the feedback loop between the pilot evaluation tasks under SP4 and the design and development tasks in SP1, SP2 and SP3. These procedures acted in both ways: from design and development to evaluation, and from evaluation to design and development.

4.4.2.1 From design and development to evaluation

The team of designers and developers on the user interfaces for the PMT frequently found situations that needed from user research and usability testing. Broader questions include:

- When (in a user's workflow) are settings changed?
- Where do users go to make changes to settings/preferences (website, browser, operating system, hardware)?
- How does the process of changing settings vary across different circumstances?
- What do users view as a preference?
- Do users distinguish between temporary preference and a permanent preference?
- This relates to saving preferences - when and how?

More granular questions for testing included measuring the ease of use of the search bar, relevance of curated categories, switching between preferences and presets, adjuster design variations, tool panels layout, etc.

At some point in each evaluation iteration, these design questions were discussed between the UX team and the SP4 team and integrated in the corresponding pilot evaluation framework (e.g. (Sainz, Chalkia, Carmona, & Montalva, 2013)).

4.4.2.2 From evaluation to design and development

The team of researchers in Cloud4all followed a number of procedures to be coordinated with the team of designers and developers working with the user interfaces. These included the following activities:

- **Before the pilot iteration started**, researchers tested the prototypes to be evaluated and several remote calls and meetings were organized with designers and developers to solve the most important usability or technical issues.
- **During pilots**, some raw data from results were distributed through SP4 email list and to specific design and development teams when required. This allowed the incorporation of user feedback into design without waiting for an official pilot results report.
- **After the pilots**, design and development teams received specific reports for each of the functional and non-functional interfaces that were evaluated.

After each iteration, all the issues found with a relation to the PMT or the PCP that were mentioned in the research reports were clustered by FhG, using the following categories:

1. **"Design"**, when the issue was supposed to be solved by changing the interaction design of one of the tools

2. **“Implementation”**, when the issue referred to something that was planned to be implemented but not yet fully working. This includes bugs.
3. **“Translation”**, when a design issue was supposedly due to problems with the translation of certain wordings in the English version. This also refers to new translations that became necessary due to other recent design changes and the introduction of new terms in the English version.

While the pilots were under way, work already continued on the user interface design of PMT and PCP, hence several aspects that caused issues had already been changed once the report was provided to the UX team.

4.4.3 User Experience with Cloud4all tools

The evaluation performed in pilots included dedicated usability testing with the PMT-PCP tools, as well as an assessment of the user experience with Cloud4all concept in general. For example, questionnaires were used to collect participants’ assessments of the usability of the PMT (see Figure 7) .

Figure 7. Results on the Perceived usability of the PMT (UMUX score) in the 1st and 2nd iterations

The results of this evaluation shows an improvement (from 60 to 80 points in a 100 scale) of the perceived usability of the PMT prototype in the 2nd iteration when compared to the one used in the 1st iteration. This result can be considered a validation of the UCD approach followed in the sense that the design-evaluation cycle have produced UIs with improved usability as perceived by end-users.

5 Conclusions

The Cloud4all project adopted an UCD approach to be applied in the design and development of interfaces and applications. This approach defined, on the one hand, a number of procedures aimed to foster the user involvement in design and research activities and, on the other hand, an interaction plan structured into three phases: context of usage and requirement analysis, conceptual design and prototyping and evaluation.

Different types of users and user groups were defined and recruited, resulting in the participation of 353 end-users, 77 developers and 45 stakeholders in research activities. This could not be possible without a trustful liaison with user groups and the dedicated recruitment plan followed by the Greek, German and Spanish pilot sites.

This document has also described the process followed by the design and development teams during the creation of preference management tools. With a clear problem statement and an approach that focuses on human diversity the resulting tools empower users to personalize their experience, adapting the interface to their own unique needs and preferences. Although the final prototypes can be now demoed and examined, it is worth to describe and analyse the techniques and activities that have been used to improve its design and the rationale behind design decisions.

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